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Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Phototherapy Among Mothers of Neonates

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ABSTRACT

An accumulation of bilirubin in the blood, known as hyperbilirubinemia, results in jaundice, a yellowish coloring of the skin and eyes. A yellowish pigment called bilirubin is created as red blood cells normally break down. Phototherapy is a safe and effective treatment for neonatal jaundice. It involves exposing the baby to special blue light, which helps their liver process and eliminates bilirubin. Phototherapy uses blue light to convert bilirubin into a form that is easier for the body to excrete through urine and stool. The descriptive study was conducted to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding phototherapy among mothers of neonates. Sample consisted of 100 mothers of neonates from N.S Memorial Institute of Medical Science, Palathara, Kollam, Kerala, sample selection was done by nonprobability purposive sampling. Data was collected using a pretested validated and reliable questionnaire on knowledge regarding phototherapy and 5point likert scale to assess the attitude regarding phototherapy. The current study's goals were to evaluate mothers of newborns' knowledge of phototherapy, their attitudes toward phototherapy, to determine the association between knowledge of mothers of neonates regarding phototherapy with selected socio demographic variables, to determine the association between attitude of mothers of neonates regarding phototherapy with selected socio demographic variables, to determine the correlation between knowledge and attitude of mothers of neonates strong adults with enhanced quality of human resource development. According to the WHO, Neonatal jaundice, also known as hyperbilirubinemia, is the yellow discoloration of a newborn's skin and eyes caused by elevated bilirubin

levels in the blood. Neonatal jaundice, also known as neonatal hyperbilirubinemia, refers to yellow staining of the skin or other

organs caused by the accumulation of bilirubin in the body. It is a common clinical problem in the neonatal

Keywords: *Hyperbilirubinemia, neonatal jaundice, phototherapy, mothers' knowledge*

INTRODUCTION

Having a new member in the family is typically an exciting, welcome event. Various factors can influence how a new baby impacts a family life, whether it is the first baby or not. All parents have fruitful ambition to have healthy children. The child inherits their parent's characters, and they are the future wealth of the nation.[1]

Infants between birth and first 28 days of life are called newborns or neonates. Globally 130 million babies are born every year. Every year about 27 million babies (20% of global births) are born in India. Neonates constitute the foundation of a nation, and no sensible government can afford to neglect their needs and rights. Healthy and sturdy babies are likely to evolve as physically and mentally period, and approximately 50%–60% of full-term infants and 80% of premature infants develop jaundice within 1 week after birth. The clinical neonatal jaundice manifests on the face at a serum bilirubin level of 5 mg/dl (1 mg/dl = 17 μ moles/l) followed by trunk at 10 – 15 mg/dl, soles or palms > 15 mg/dl. Over two – third of neonates develop clinical jaundice and by adult standards almost all neonates are 'jaundiced' during early days of life.[2]

Yellow discoloration is first evident on the skin of face, nasolabial folds and tip of the nose. In many infants, neonatal jaundice is a benign condition.

However, severe hyperbilirubinemia may cause acute bilirubin encephalopathy (ABE) or kernicterus,

which may progress to nerve deafness, choreoathetoid cerebral palsy, intellectual disability and even death. Early detection and timely treatment of neonatal jaundice are key strategies to prevent ABE and kernicterus. However, neonatal jaundice generally peaks on the 5th–7th day after birth, at which time most healthy full-term infants have been discharged from hospital. Therefore, most neonatal jaundice occurs at home.[3]

Mothers are frequently the first to notice jaundice, its progression, and early symptoms of ABE and kernicterus because they are the primary caregivers of newborns following hospital discharge. They are essential to managing newborn jaundice in a way that produces positive results.

Jaundice happens when your baby's blood has too much bilirubin. Bilirubin is a chemical that body makes when it breaks down old red blood cells. Your liver normally filters bilirubin from the blood. If baby's liver hasn't developed enough to get rid of bilirubin, it can start to build up. This buildup of bilirubin causes your baby's skin to look yellow.

Most babies develop jaundice in their first few days of life. This is because it takes a few days for your baby's liver to develop and get better at removing bilirubin.[4]

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A descriptive study on knowledge and attitude regarding phototherapy among mothers of neonates in selected hospitals

at Kollam district.

OBJECTIVE

- To assess the knowledge regarding phototherapy among mothers of neonates
- To assess the attitude regarding phototherapy among mothers of neonates
- To determine the association between knowledge of mothers of neonates regarding phototherapy with selected socio demographic variables.
- To determine the association between attitude of mothers of neonates regarding phototherapy with selected socio demographic variables.

Hypothesis

- H1: There will be significant association between knowledge of mothers of neonates regarding phototherapy with selected socio demographic variables.
- H2: There will be significant association between attitude of mothers of neonates regarding phototherapy with selected socio demographic variables.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Population and Study Design

The research design adopted for the study was Nonexperimental descriptive design.

The setting of the present study was Neonatal units and Pay words of N.S Memorial Institute of Medical Sciences, Kollam. The setting was selected purposively. NSMIMS is a multispecialty hospital, with 400 bedding, with all general departments and super specialties with 24-hour casualty and critical care units. Pediatric department facilities consist of pediatric wards, tertiary level neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), and pediatric intensive care unit (PICU) along with ten percent

bed allocation in all pay wards. The neonatal intensive care unit consists of 12 beds for admitting neonates with various medical and surgical illnesses. About 8 – 10 neonates are admitted in NICU regularly.[5]

Inclusion Criteria

- Mothers of neonates who were admitted during the time of data collection.
- Mothers who know to read and write Malayalam or English language.

Exclusion Criteria

The present study excluded:

- Mother who are not willing to participate
- Mother of neonate with critically ill
- Mothers who are health professionals.

STUDY SETTING AND SAMPLE SELECTION

The setting of the present study was Neonatal units and Pay words of N.S Memorial Institute of Medical Sciences, Kollam. The setting was selected purposively. NSMIMS is a multi-specialty hospital, 400 bedded, with all general departments and super specialty with 24-hour casualty and critical care units.[6]

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance for conducting the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee and Institutional Research Committee. Informed consent from each subject was taken after detailed explanation of the study and confidentiality was ensured.

Statistical Analysis

All the data were analysed by descriptive and inferential statistics, and a chi-square test was computed to find the knowledge and attitude regarding phototherapy among mothers of neonates. The computed and tabulated data are presented here according to the

objectives.[7,8]

Among 62% of the mothers were from

nuclear family, 65% were housewives, 70% of the mothers had average knowledge, 53% had favorable attitude.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of mothers according to type of family. n=100

Type of family	Frequency (f)	%
Nuclear family	62	62%
Joint family	36	36%
Extended family	2	2%

Table 1 shows that more than half of the subjects (62 %) belonged to nuclear family.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of mother according to occupation. n=100

Occupation of mother	Frequency(f)	%
Housewives	65	65%
Government employee	9	9%
Private employee	20	20%
Others	6	6%

Table 2 shows that more than half (65%) of the mothers were housewives.

Table 3: Frequency and percentage distribution of subjects according to knowledge regarding phototherapy. n=100.

Knowledge of mothers	Mean	Standard deviation	Frequency	percentage
Poor (1-6)			15	15%
Average (7-12)	9.484	2.833	70	70%
Good (13-18)			15	15%

Table 3 shows that nearly three by fourth of the subjects (70%) have average knowledge regarding phototherapy.

Table 4: Frequency and percentage distribution of subjects according to attitude regarding phototherapy. n=100

Attitude of mothers	Mean	Standard deviation	Frequency	Percentage
Unfavorable (125)	51.5	5.9598	0	47%
Moderately favorable (2650)			47	0%
Favorable (5175)			53	53%

Table 5: Association between knowledge of mothers regarding phototherapy with socio demographic variables. n= 100

Socio demographic variable	Df	Chi square	P value
Age of mother	6	11.352	0.078

Religion	4	16.569**	0.002
Area of living	4	3.110	0.540
Type of family	4	6.144	0.189
Education	6	6.279	0.393
Occupation of mother	6	29.357***	0.000
Number of children	4	9.758*	0.045
Income	4	10.211*	0.037
Information regarding phototherapy	4	4.270	0.37

Significant at $p < 0.05$ level. *Significant at $p < 0.01$ level. Significant at $p < 0.001$**
 Table 5 shows that there was a significant association between religion ($\chi^2 = 16.569$, $p=0.002$), occupation of mother ($\chi^2=29.357$, $p=0.000$), number of children ($\chi^2=9.758$, $p=0.045$), income ($\chi^2=10.21$, $p=0.037$) with knowledge regarding phototherapy among mothers of neonates.

Table 6: Association between attitude of mothers regarding phototherapy with socio demographic variables. $n=100$

Socio demographic variable	Df	Chi square	P value
Age of mother	3	2.894	0.408
Religion	2	2.102	0.350
Area of living	2	3.106	0.212
Type of family	2	2.682	0.262
Education	3	10.117*	0.018
Occupation of mother	3	4.240	0.237
Number of children	2	5.686	0.058
Income	2	3.285	0.194
Information regarding phototherapy	2	3.573	0.168

Significant at $p < 0.05$ level.

Table 6 shows that there was a significant association between educational status ($\chi^2 = 10.117$, $p=0.018$) with attitude regarding phototherapy among mothers of neonat.

Table 7: Correlation between knowledge and attitude of mothers regarding phototherapy. $n=100$

Variables	Correlation	P value
Knowledge of Mother s	0.329	0.001
Attitude of Mothers		

Table 7 shows that there was a significant weak positive ($r=0.329$) correlation between knowledge and

attitude of mothers regarding phototherapy ($p=0.001$), which indicates that as the knowledge increases attitude

also increases.

DISCUSSION

The discussion according to objectives of present study and supported by similar studies is as follows:

The present study reveals that 15% of the subjects had poor levels of knowledge and 70% of the subjects had average levels of knowledge and 15% of the subjects had good knowledge. These findings is supported by a study conducted by Mahima Mary Punnen, Anila KP, S Deepa on knowledge and practice of mothers in care of newborns receiving phototherapy at selected hospitals at Kochi, Kerala, reveals that (72%) of the mothers had average knowledge, (16%) had good knowledge and (12%) had poor knowledge.[9,10]

In the present study, 47% of the mothers had moderately favourable attitude and 53% of the mothers had favourable attitude. These findings are supported by a study conducted by Al- Zamili and Saadon in a hospital study among 250 mothers in Iraq, reveals 64% of the respondents had a positive attitude towards neonatal jaundice.

A nonexperimental study was conducted by Shaheena MN and Nithya KS to assess the Knowledge regarding phototherapy among postnatal mothers. The investigators had selected 35 mothers of newborns. This study was conducted at district Model hospital, Peroorkada,

Thiruvananthapuram. The result shows that there was association between number of children ($p=0.013$) with knowledge of mothers regarding phototherapy.

In the present study there was significant association between educational status

($p= 0.018$) with attitude of mothers regarding phototherapy. A descriptive cross-sectional study of Egube, et al. Among 389 Mothers in Nigeria showed that there was association between age ($p= 0.015$) and educational status ($p=0.001$) with attitude of mothers regarding phototherapy.

A descriptive study conducted by Mahima Mary Punnen, Anila KP, S Deepa to assess the knowledge and attitude of mothers in care of newborns receiving phototherapy. There was a positive correlation ($r=0.819$, $p=0.01$) found between level of knowledge and attitude.[11]

CONCLUSION

In this present study Mean, standard deviation and correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer among women showed that there was a significant weak positive ($r=0.127$, $p=0.209$) correlation between knowledge and attitude of women regarding cervical cancer which indicates as the knowledge increases, attitude also increases. Association between knowledge regarding cervical cancer and selected demographic variables showed that the knowledge of women regarding cervical cancer and selected socio demographic variables found no significant association. The findings of this study may provide information that, among the women of Pampuram ward (number 10) of Kalluvathukkal village, majority were having average knowledge and average attitude regarding cervical cancer. In order to increase the knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer, we conducted an awareness program regarding cervical cancer with the help of brochure.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. (2022).

- Cervical cancer.* <https://www.who.int>
2. Zhao, F. H., Hu, S. Y., Zhang, X., Li, L., Zhang, Q., Dong, L., et al. (2012). Cervical cancer is the second most common female malignant tumour globally and a serious threat to women's health. *Cancer Biology & Medicine*, 9(1), 9–17.
 3. World Health Organization. (2023). *Cervical cancer.* <https://www.who.int>
 4. World Health Organization. (2020). *Global strategy to accelerate the elimination of cervical cancer as a public health problem.* <https://www.who.int>
 5. National Cancer Institute. (2022). *Cervical cancer—patient version.* <https://www.cancer.gov>
 6. Cleveland Clinic. (2023). *Cervical cancer: Causes, symptoms, diagnosis, prevention, and treatment.* <https://my.clevelandclinic.org>
 7. Kerala Health Department. (2023). *Cancer screening survey among women in Kerala: Final report 2023.* Directorate of Health Services.
 8. Taneja, B., Chawla, N., Awasthi, A. A., et al. (2021). Knowledge, attitude, and practice on cervical cancer and screening among women in India: A systematic review of 7,688 participants. *Cancer Control.* <https://doi.org/10.1177/10732748211013454>
 9. Shrestha, J., Saha, R., & Tripathi, N. (2013). Knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding cervical cancer screening among women visiting a teaching hospital in Nepal. *Journal of Nepal Health Research Council*, 11(23), 42–46.
 10. Raychaudhuri, S., & Mandal, S. (2012). Knowledge, attitude, and practice of cervical cancer screening among women in a tertiary care hospital of India. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynaecology*, 1(1), 9–13.
 11. Hoque, M. E., & Hoque, M. (2009). Knowledge of and attitude towards cervical cancer among female university students in South Africa. *Southern African Journal of Epidemiology and Infection*, 24(1), 21–24.